

BEYOND OPEN DOORS: CHILE'S PATH TOWARD INVESTMENT SECURITY IN AN ERA OF GREAT POWER COMPETITION

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I. Introduction

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) has for decades been one of the main drivers of economic globalisation. Due to technological advancements and a favourable political environment in the second half of the twentieth century, the cross-border fragmentation of production, whereby different production stages of a given production process are located in several countries, has significantly increased in recent decades (Brooks, 2007; Hanson, 2001). Yet, the last few years have seen a notable shift in the way many governments approach their policy towards FDI. Namely, a growing number of governments across the world have started to implement new or tighten already existing Investment Screening Mechanisms (ISMs) (Bauerle Danzman & Meunier, 2023; Calcara & Poletti, 2023; Doppen et al., 2024). An ISM is a legal tool that host governments use to review and potentially block FDI if such an investment represents a potential risk to national security.

There is a widespread view in the academic literature that the ongoing shift toward ISMs can be explained by the re-emergence of China as a great power and its new role as a leading global investor (Bauerle Danzman & Meunier, 2023; Canes-Wrone et al., 2020; Meunier, 2019; Tingley et al., 2015). Many of the countries that have recently tightened their investment screening mechanisms in the context of China's rise share a common concern rooted in the fact that China is not a security ally,¹ which renders FDI originating from Beijing inherently more sensitive (Meunier, 2014). Acquisitions by a non-allied state in dual-use or otherwise strategic sectors risk enabling espionage or the transfer of cutting-edge technologies to a country outside one's alliance framework (Meunier, 2018). In a similar vein, excessive dependence on a non-allied state as a source of FDI may generate vulnerabilities to economic coercion (Otero-Iglesias & Weissenegger, 2019). These concerns are further magnified by China's unique politico-economic system, which features a significant presence of State-Owned Enterprises (SOEs) and Privately Owned Enterprises (POEs) with close ties to the central government in Beijing, making it difficult for host governments to determine whether a given investment serves commercial or strategic purposes (Meunier, 2015, 2019).

¹ The concept of "ally" used here refers to a security alliance, denoting states bound by a formal treaty commitment to provide mutual assistance — typically military — in the event of an attack on either party (e.g., NATO or the US-Japan Security Treaty). FDI flows into sensitive sectors originating from an allied country are likely to generate fewer concerns and less political backlash than those coming from a non-allied or even hostile state.

Since the 2010s, this trend has been observed predominantly in countries in North America and Europe. Yet, recent years have shown that the use of FDI screening is likely to spread to other parts of the globe, including Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC). In 2020, Brazilian congressman Luiz Philippe de Orleans e Bragança (PSL-SP) introduced a bill proposing restrictions on the entry of foreign capital into certain sectors of the Brazilian economy (Agência Câmara de Notícias, 2020). In a similar vein, in December 2020, a group of Chilean politicians, led by Socialist deputy Jaime Naranjo, drafted a bill to institutionalize Chile's first formal investment screening mechanism (ISM) (Naranjo, 2020). Lastly, since December 2023, Mexican policymakers have been collaborating with their US counterparts in an effort to develop a foreign investment screening regime in Mexico, similar to the Committee on Foreign Investment in the United States (CFIUS) (Egan et al., 2023).

Latin American countries represent an interesting case for debate on ISMs. On the one hand, the region's economies are heavily dependent on foreign capital and continue to attract investors from major economies. (ECLAC, 2025a). At the same time, however, most of the countries in the region currently have very limited and often underdeveloped regulations for controlling the entrance of foreign capital on national security grounds. In a context of intensified great power competition between Beijing and Washington, in which both actors aim to increase their economic leverage in the region and gain access to the region's key economic sectors (Urdinez, 2025), the region's countries face an acute need to refine their current FDI regulations.

The case of Chile exemplifies this trend. Chile has been China's main investment destination in the region in the period 2018-2023 (Myers et al., 2024). In addition, Chile has been repeatedly viewed as a country with the most favorable institutional architecture for investors, due to its solid rule of law and reliable financial services (Smith & Rabin, 2022). These factors facilitate FDI attraction to the country. Yet, the potential mitigation of negative security externalities of FDI is challenging, as Chile has very few regulations to review FDI and lacks a formal ISM. As further explained below, several recent Chinese FDI projects have exposed a significant regulatory gap in Chile's legal architecture for screening incoming foreign investment and sparked renewed policy discussions on the need to establish a formal ISM. The United States has also repeatedly raised concerns over Beijing's growing economic foothold in Chile (Lautaro, 2025; Troncoso, 2025). The bill proposed in 2020 and debated in parliament in 2021 has since stalled, and it remains to be seen whether the current government will take it any further.

To offer a better understanding of the main challenges that Chile and other Latin American countries face in relation to ISMs, this report has two main objectives. First, it aims to explain whether and why Chile needs to institutionalize a formal ISM to continue benefiting from FDI while preserving national security. Second, the report focuses on the main institutional and political obstacles in achieving such a goal. The analysis of recent FDI flows and an overview of existing regulations in Chile point to a need to establish a formal ISM. However, such a mechanism should be conceived as a preventive tool applicable to specific FDI deals regardless of their origin, rather than as a form of backlash

against growing Chinese investment, as the majority of such deals carry limited immediate implications for national security.

Regarding the main challenges in establishing an ISM, enhancing awareness among policymakers and the broader public will be essential. Chile must also develop a more comprehensive framework for defining national economic interests by identifying sectors critical to both economic development and national security. This strategic prioritization will inform which sectors fall under the ISM's review. Finally, Chile will need to designate a lead institution to chair the review committee and determine which government bodies (ministries and agencies) will participate. This organizational structure should leverage existing expertise and institutional capacity within relevant ministries.

The following section outlines the methodological approach adopted in this paper, including the main data sources used for the analysis. In light of the growing presence of Chinese companies in Chile and the relevance of this trend for debates on ISM, the first part of Section III examines the main FDI trends in the country, with a particular focus on Chinese investment. To demonstrate that the current Chilean legal landscape falls short in addressing the security challenges posed by incoming FDI, the second part of that section offers an overview of the existing regulatory framework governing foreign investment. These elements together allow for the identification of the main challenges associated with establishing an ISM in Chile, in the rest of Section III.

II. Methodology

To achieve the above-mentioned goals, the paper proceeds in the following manner. First, to explain whether and why the country needs an ISM, the paper examines the most recent FDI trends, with particular emphasis on FDI from China. It does so by using the most recent version of the Regional Repository of Chinese Investments in Latin America, which offers the most up-to-date and comprehensive data on Chinese FDI in the region over the last two decades. In particular, the paper focuses on the following characteristics of Chinese FDI: (1) sectoral concentration (sensitive vs. non-sensitive industries), (2) type of FDI (M&A vs. greenfield), and (3) type of investor (SOE vs. POE). This analysis allows us to identify the main potential risks linked to FDI while also pushing back against hawkish interpretations that Chinese FDI inherently represents an imminent security risk.

Second, the paper uses legal documents to map the current regulatory landscape on FDI in the country. In doing so, the paper shows the extent to which challenges arising from FDI can (or cannot) be addressed by current regulation. Existing gaps in the regulation, which often cannot address these risks, then justify the need for implementing an ISM. By assessing the existing risks linked to FDI and current shortcomings in Chilean legislation, the final part identifies the main institutional and political challenges in Chile's path toward a more formal ISM.

III. Case study

The Chilean economy has long been one of the most attractive Latin American countries to foreign investors. Despite a relatively small domestic market compared to other countries, between 2005 and 2024, Chile has been among the top five FDI destinations in Latin America (ECLAC, 2025b). The most targeted sectors by FDI are mining, electricity, gas and water, and financial services (U.S. Department of State, 2024). While companies from Western countries, such as Canada, the United States, and Spain, have been among the largest investors in the country (Santander Trade Markets, n.d.), the emergence of China as the main capital provider has been indisputable in recent years. In fact, in 2019, China became the leading foreign investor in Chile for the first time (Alonso, 2020).

The attractiveness of the Chilean market for foreign investors can be explained principally by a stable legal and regulatory architecture and high-quality financial services. While these factors facilitate FDI attraction, Chile's current legal framework leaves it largely ill-equipped to address the potential non-economic negative impacts of incoming FDI. At present, the country does not have a formal ISM, and the existing restrictions on FDI concern only a very limited number of sectors. In a context of increasing FDI from China in sensitive sectors, coupled with intensifying US-China competition, the pressure Chile faces to refine its regulatory framework for FDI is unprecedented. The emergence of the Chilean debate on the need for an ISM is driven by both the rise of China as the country's leading investor and the growing perception among segments of

the Chilean political class that this trend raises significant security concerns. Given the centrality of China in these debates, the following section offers a detailed overview of recent Chinese FDI trends in Chile.

Chinese FDI in Chile

Despite the burgeoning Sino-Chilean trade relationship since the early 2000s, Beijing long focused on investing in larger regional markets, particularly Brazil. Substantial Chinese FDI to Chile began only in 2018 and has remained largely constant since then. Between 2018 and 2023, Chile emerged as the top recipient of Chinese FDI in the region (Myers et al. 2024). Over the period 2010-2024, China invested \$21 billion in the country. While Chinese investment peaked between 2018 and 2021, significant capital continued flowing to Chile in 2023 and 2024 (Urđinez & Myers, 2025).

Looking at the sectoral concentration of Chinese FDI, energy stands out as the main targeted sector. Since 2010, Chinese companies have initiated eighteen FDI projects in Chile for a total value of \$10 billion. The total invested amount in energy accounts for 48% of total Chinese FDI in Chile between 2010 and 2024. Other main sectors include infrastructure (23% of total Chinese FDI between 2010 and 2024) and mining (20%). This overview demonstrates that 91% of total Chinese FDI has concentrated in so-called sensitive sectors, where energy, infrastructure, and mining traditionally belong.

Chinese Annual FDI in Chile (in million USD), 2010-2024

Year	Number of deals	Amount invested (in million USD)
2010	1	18
2011	1	11
2012	3	63
2013	3	45
2014	2	36
2015	1	286
2016	2	359
2017	3	99
2018	8	5884
2019	4	3408
2020	3	5100
2021	5	4561
2022	3	871
2023	7	1046
2024	5	948

To be sure, the presence of Chinese FDI in sensitive sectors should not be interpreted as necessarily posing security risks to the Chilean economy or society. A more detailed analysis of Chinese FDI projects in the country reveals rather limited immediate risks in practice. In the energy sector, many Chinese investments involved the installation of solar parks or wind turbines

— assets that carry relatively limited immediate security implications. In the infrastructure sector, several projects concerned the construction of railways between major cities or the building of hospitals. In such cases, it can be argued that participation in construction, as opposed to full operational control over a given facility, can hardly be considered a security risk when the

Distribution of Chinese FDI in Chile by Sector, 2010-2024

Sector	Number of deals	Total amount invested (in million USD)
energy	18	10 078
Infrastructure	13	4 951
Real Estate	8	604
Agroindustry	7	1 096
Mining	3	4 305
ICT	2	174

entity ultimately managing or operating the hospital or rail line remains Chilean. Similarly, in the mining sector, most deals involved only minority concessions. Taken together, these trends suggest that the overwhelming majority of Chinese FDI in strategic sectors does not represent a significant threat to Chilean national security. That said, the concerns driving the Chilean debate are not entirely unfounded. While they remain largely rooted in perception rather than a pattern of existing identifiable risks, there exist a limited number of cases where genuine security exposure can be identified.

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The most notorious and relevant case for ISM-related debates involves Chinese SOE State Grid. Through two acquisitions made in 2019 and 2020, State Grid became a major player in the electricity distribution market in Chile, now controlling electricity distribution to almost 60% of Chilean households (Systep, 2020). Electricity distribution is part of critical infrastructure essential for the proper functioning of the national economy and society. Therefore, substantial control over this service concentrated in the hands of a foreign entity can indeed be seen as concerning. As detailed below, it was precisely the State Grid case that significantly triggered the ISM debate and legislative action in Chile.

As for the type of FDI coming from China to Chile, the dataset used in this report distinguishes between three types. First, greenfield investment occurs when a foreign entity establishes new operations in the host country. M&A corresponds to a situation in which the investing foreign company acquires full or partial ownership of an existing facility from a domestic or another foreign company. Finally, “construction” refers to projects in which Chinese companies execute large-scale infrastructure works — such as roads, bridges, ports, or

power plants — and are remunerated for this work, but do not retain ownership of the completed infrastructure, which remains in the hands of the state or a private contractor.²

Between 2010 and 2024, 31% of deals (16) came in the form of greenfield investment, 29% (15 deals) as M&A, and 39% as construction. Yet, when looking at the actual amount invested, the dominance of M&A emerges, as 58% of the total amount invested by Chinese firms in Chile in the above-mentioned period came in the form of M&A (\$12.3 billion). Construction accounted for 35% (\$7.4 billion) and greenfield investment for 7% (\$1.5 billion).

² See page 6 of Methodology for the Creation and Development of The ICLAC Chinese Investment Database and Interactive Map (Urdinez & Myers, 2025)

Chinese FDI in Chile by type of FDI (greenfield, M&A, construction)

Type of FDI	Number of deals	Total FDI invested
Construction	20	7 405
Greenfield	16	1 478
M&A	15	12 325

In the context of China's international investment strategy, the ownership structure of the investing firm is a particularly relevant variable. As the existing academic literature has pointed out, the blurred lines between the public and private spheres in China make it difficult for host governments to determine whether a given Chinese investment serves commercial or strategic purposes (Reilly, 2013; Meunier, 2014). Another line of research has demonstrated that investment decisions of Chinese SOEs abroad can be significantly guided by Beijing's geopolitical considerations in the host country (Duanmu & Urdinez, 2018; Urdinez et al., 2016). These concerns have been behind the preoccupation of many foreign governments facing a sudden increase in FDI from China.

In the case of Chile, several Chinese SOEs or POEs with close ties to the central government in Beijing have been involved in important FDI deals in Chile. The list includes firms such as COFCO, ZTE, Bank of China, and Huawei. As mentioned above, the most important case involves State Grid. The relevance of the ownership structure of Chinese companies to the sensitivity perceived in host countries was also reflected in Chilean parliamentary debates. For instance, when discussing the bill proposal to establish a formal ISM in July 2021 in the context of State Grid's acquisitions, Chilean Deputy Jaime Mulet stated: "We are talking about a Chinese state company, from the People's Republic of China, a country which is not precisely a democracy. From my

standpoint, this is a concerning situation" (Cámara de Diputados, 2021).

The analysis of trends in Chinese FDI in Chile demonstrates several key findings. First, the vast majority of FDI from Beijing has indeed concentrated in sectors that may pose some risks to national security and which are often included in ISMs. Second, however, the real security implications of this FDI in such sectors are for now rather limited, though exceptional deals can indeed potentially cause significant harm to national security. Third, a non-negligible share of investing companies in Chile are Chinese SOEs, which opens debates about the real intentions behind such FDI. Lastly, the vast majority of Chinese FDI in the country came in the form of M&A, which implies greater relevance for national security. However, greenfield investment still accounts for almost 10% of the total value invested by China in the selected period, suggesting that this type of FDI should also be part of future ISM design.

Overall, the analysis of investment flows from China reveals that an ISM in Chile is needed as a preventive tool likely to be used only in rare cases, such as that of State Grid. In addition, the prospect of China deploying economic coercion against Chile remains for now a rather unlikely scenario. For instance, while China accounts for almost 40% of Chilean exports — a position of considerable asymmetric advantage — Beijing has to date never leveraged this position to pressure Chile

into adopting specific policies or stances, unlike in its relations with other small states.³

Current regulations on FDI in Chile

Chile is one of the very few OECD countries that currently does not have a formal ISM. Under Chilean regulation, foreign investors enjoy equal treatment with national firms in almost all economic sectors and activities. This non-discriminatory treatment is also established by Decree Law No. 600 from 1974, which identifies FDI as a necessary complement to national investment to achieve the country's economic development. The Decree also establishes the Foreign Investment Committee (Comité de Inversiones Extranjeras), which is the sole state agency authorized to accept foreign capital contributions, grant repatriation rights for invested capital and profits, and approve foreign investment contracts under DL 600.

Yet, the functions of this Committee are rather limited in the context of the current paper, as it functions as a facilitation and registration body rather than a screening mechanism. At the same time, the Committee's composition could be leveraged as a potential model for building a future ISM Review Committee. According to DL 600, the Foreign Investment Committee is composed of the Minister of Economy, Development and Reconstruction; the Minister of Finance; the Minister of Foreign Affairs; the Minister of the relevant sector when investment applications relate to matters concerning ministries not represented on the Committee; the Director of the National Planning Office; the Executive Vice President of the Production Development Corporation (CORFO); the President of the Central Bank of

Chile; and the President of the Confederation of Production and Commerce.

Another foundational regulation is Chapter XIV of the Compendium of International Exchange Regulations of the Central Bank of Chile, which defines FDI as follows: "Any act, agreement or contract by virtue of which a party acquires, with foreign currency from abroad or with the proceeds of its liquidation in the country, ownership, or the right to use, enjoy, possess or merely hold securities, commercial instruments, shares, corporate rights and any other class of titles or securities, or real estate or movable property." This definition could be leveraged and integrated within a formal ISM, alongside a formal definition of the term "foreign investor."

Lastly, the Law on the Defense of Free Competition (DL 211, 1973) empowers the National Economic Prosecutor's Office (Fiscalía Nacional Económica, FNE) to review large mergers and acquisitions on competition grounds, ensuring that transactions do not distort market dynamics by conferring excessive market power to a single entity. However, this provision is limited to economic competition concerns and does not address potential national security implications of FDI transactions. This institutional gap has been acknowledged in Chilean legislative debates on a potential ISM. As Deputy Jaime Mulet (Social Green Regionalist Federation) observed: "Neither the Ministry of National Defense, nor FNE, nor any other state body can study the geopolitical consequences that a given acquisition may have, a topic we are discussing today" (Cámara de Diputados, 2021).

The specific sectoral regulations currently in place in Chile are limited and exclude many key strategic sectors. At the time of writing, restrictions on foreign own-

³ For a comprehensive overview of China's coercion against other states, see Cha (2023).

ership exist in maritime transport and coastal shipping,⁴ industrial fishing,⁵ and domestic air carriers.⁶ Similar restrictions apply to television concessions and media ownership.⁷ Another regulation limits foreign ownership of land and property in border areas. State-owned lands within 10 kilometers of the border or 5 kilometers of the coast can only be acquired by Chilean nationals or legal entities, with foreigners domiciled in Chile requiring prior Navy approval for coastal lands. Nationals from bordering countries are prohibited from acquiring property in designated border zones unless specifically authorized by Presidential decree approved by the Ministries of Interior, Foreign Affairs, and National Defense.⁸

Chile's legal framework for mining declares absolute state ownership over all mineral deposits, including strategic minerals like lithium and copper.⁹ However, these laws distinguish between concessionable minerals (most minerals including copper), which can be freely exploited by any person—Chilean or foreign—through mining concessions granted as constitutionally-protected real property rights, and non-concessionable strategic minerals (primarily lithium and hydrocarbons), which can only be exploited directly by the State or through discretionary special operating contracts or administrative concessions authorized by Presidential decree. As such, there are no nationality-based restrictions on foreign ownership of regular mining concessions, but the non-concession regime for strategic minerals grants the State significant dis-

cretionary authority to control who can access these resources and under what conditions. While this mechanism primarily serves resource sovereignty rather than national security purposes, the Presidential authority to approve, condition, or terminate special operating contracts for strategic minerals could function as a de facto sector-specific investment screening tool. However, it falls short of a comprehensive ISM since it only applies to specific non-concessionable substances and lacks the broader national security review framework typical of modern ISMs.

Despite the existence of several sector-specific regulations restricting inward FDI, the absence of a formal ISM has exposed Chile to a number of undesirable consequences. In the absence of such a mechanism, FDI projects in sectors not covered by existing regulations have on occasion been blocked through informal and legally ambiguous administrative decisions, characterized by a notable lack of transparency. The most prominent cases of this kind involved Chinese companies that had won contracts for projects deemed sensitive, yet which could not be formally reviewed due to the absence of an ISM. Two cases stand out in particular: the planned submarine cable to be operated by Huawei connecting Chile with China, and the project by Chinese-German company Aisino to produce Chilean passports and national identity cards.¹⁰ Both projects triggered politically motivated opposition and were ultimately blocked on largely unsubstantiated grounds, including claims of cost-ineffectiveness, technical infea-

4 See Decreto Ley 2222 from 1978

5 Ley 18.892, Ley General de Pesca y Acuicultura.

6 Decreto Ley 2.564 (1979), Ley de Aeronáutica Civil

7 Ley 18.838 (1989), Ley General de Telecomunicaciones.

8 Decreto Ley 1.939 (1977), Normas sobre Adquisición, Administración y Disposición de Bienes del Estado.

9 See the Constitution (Article 19 N°24), the Constitutional Organic Law on Mining Concessions (Ley 18.097), and the Mining Code (Ley 18.248)

10 For more on these cases, see: Bórquez & López (2025)

sibility, or alleged non-compliance with administrative requirements on the part of the companies involved. Such opaque and legally questionable practices generated diplomatic friction with China, whose government protested what it characterized as discriminatory treatment of its companies (See Montt Strabucchi et al., 2023). It is precisely to avoid the recurrence of such scenarios that Chile requires a formal ISM — one that would equip the state with legitimate and transparent tools to review potentially sensitive FDI transactions, while simultaneously providing greater regulatory predictability for incoming foreign investors.

The legal analysis in this section reveals that Chile's current legal architecture includes several tools to restrict foreign ownership in selected economic activities and sectors, as well as existing state bodies responsible for supervising and controlling FDI. These elements could be leveraged in building a more formal ISM, which is nonetheless needed as existing regulations fall short of adequately safeguarding Chilean national security. This shortfall is primarily due to limited sectoral coverage, which excludes many key sectors frequently targeted by FDI, such as energy, critical infrastructure, and telecommunications.

Towards Chilean ISM

The conclusions drawn from the FDI and legal analyses above point to a clear need for Chile to establish a formal ISM. The recent surge in FDI has frequently targeted strategic sectors of the economy. Moreover, several of the transactions mentioned above have resulted in significant foreign control of basic services indispensable for the functioning of the Chilean economy and society (e.g., electricity distribution). As examples from other countries demonstrate, excessive economic dependence on a foreign country can be leveraged by the latter during conflictual political disputes or diplomatic tensions.¹¹ Some of the Chilean political actors

pushing for the establishment of an ISM have raised concerns about precisely such a use of economic coercion on the part of China (see below). While the nature of Chilean-Chinese relations has so far precluded any resort to such measures, this scenario cannot be entirely ruled out, even if it remains rather unlikely.

The legal analysis of the existing regulatory architecture shows that Chile's current FDI regime offers very limited tools to address such threats. Many key sectors do not currently fall under existing legal restrictions limiting foreign ownership, and existing state bodies lack the authority to review or block FDI on national security or geopolitical grounds. Therefore, given recent FDI trends in the country, coupled with the currently insufficient legal framework for FDI regulation, it can be concluded that establishing a formal ISM is becoming a clear necessity for Chile.

In this context, it should be noted that establishing an ISM is not meant to antagonize political relations with home governments of major investors, nor is it expected to deter much-needed FDI. Rather, an ISM should be used to strengthen Chile's current regulatory framework and provide the capacity for state intervention in instances that warrant it, which would likely be limited to specific FDI transactions. A more robust FDI regulatory framework could only enhance Chile's already strong reputation for legal certainty, which has historically served as a positive attraction mechanism for foreign investors.

Current debates on ISM in Chile

With the bill proposed by Chilean politicians in December 2020, Chile became the first Latin American country where policymakers seriously discussed the establishment of a formal ISM. The bill was debated during a parliamentary hearing in July 2021, with participation from numerous key actors in Chilean politics. The na-

11 This includes China's economic coercion against Australia (Bassi, 2025) and Lithuania (Reynolds & Goodman, 2022)

ture of the bill and its underlying motivations indicate that the Chilean case aligns with a broader global trend in which security considerations are becoming increasingly salient in debates about FDI. The bill aims to “establish a formal rule of authorization, through a qualified quorum law, in cases where a foreign state acquires ownership of those companies, regardless of their legal nature, that provide public utility services or whose shutdown would cause serious harm to the health, economy of the country, supply to the population, or national security” (Cámara de Diputados, 2020).

As discussed above, the initiative originated following two acquisitions by Chinese SOE State Grid in the electricity sector. The parliamentary debate in July 2021 revealed that Chilean legislators view Chinese FDI as particularly concerning due to characteristics of the Chinese political regime, as the previous quote by Jaime Mulet demonstrates. Such concerns align with the view that there is something inherently different about Chinese FDI (Meunier, 2018), which in turn leads host governments to adapt their FDI screening regimes. As Chilean Deputy Daniel Núñez (Communist Party) stated: “Would this session occur if the CGE company were acquired by capital from the US or European countries? I do not think so. It seems that the issue is related to the origin of the capital. That is to say, Chinese investment is different from North American, Italian, or Swiss investment” (Cámara de Diputados, 2021). Such views suggest that the emerging push for an ISM in Chile is not driven by concerns about the security externalities of foreign investment in general, but rather by the perception that the growing presence of Chinese firms in the country carries distinct and potentially adverse political consequences.

The 2021 parliamentary debate on the need for an ISM, triggered by the State Grid acquisitions, brought together legislators from across the political spectrum, with positions broadly following ideological lines. Deputies from the Socialist Party and the Social Green Regionalist Federation expressed strong support for establishing a formal ISM, framing Chinese FDI in critical infrastructure as a genuine threat to national sover-

eignty and security. Communist deputies, by contrast, urged caution, questioning whether the debate reflected legitimate security concerns or rather an ideological bias against Chinese capital specifically (Cámara de Diputados, 2021). It should also be noted that, based on the available evidence, the debate appears to have remained largely confined to the legislative arena, with little to no meaningful participation from other key stakeholders — most notably business and industry associations, whose positions on an eventual ISM remain unclear.

The potential security externalities of Chinese FDI perceived by Chilean legislators also stem from the highly asymmetric nature of Chile's relationship with Beijing, rendering Santiago potentially vulnerable to economic coercion. These concerns were articulated by Deputy Jaime Naranjo in 2020, when referring to State Grid's acquisition of Chilean electricity company CGE: “In this context, the Chinese state will control the supply to 3.7 million households nationwide, that is, 57% of the country. From a geopolitical standpoint, it should not be overlooked that utility service companies are natural monopolies, with all the complexity that entails. Additionally, it should not be forgotten that China is the main destination for exports, which presents a complex situation in the event of a conflict” (Cámara de Diputados, 2020).

While ISM has become an increasingly frequent topic in policy debates and media discourse (San Martín, 202), the bill has since stalled and has not yet materialized into law. Moreover, both the bill and the 2021 parliamentary debate suggest that the proposed legislation remains at an early stage of development, leaving several critical design elements unresolved. The bill lacks clarity on several critical design elements: which specific sectors should be covered by the regulation, the composition of the review authority, and the minimum threshold that would trigger review in a given transaction. These three factors are essential components of ISM design and will be discussed in greater detail below.

In the Chilean case, the ongoing process would benefit from establishing a working group composed of legal professionals and policy analysts with expertise in FDI regulation, as well as experts from like-minded countries with existing formal ISMs. This would facilitate knowledge transfer and inform the preparation of a comprehensive bill proposal that addresses all necessary aspects of ISM design.

Relatedly, the potential benefits of ISM should also be disseminated more widely among the Chilean public. As the graph below shows, 73% of Chilean citizens surveyed by ICLAC in 2024 believe that Chile should

establish one, compared to 27% who oppose it. When asked which sectors should be subject to screening by an ISM, the most frequently cited include: copper, lithium, and electricity distribution. This shows that the general population has a solid knowledge regarding the need to establish ISM. More efforts should be done to further deepen citizens' understanding about specific mechanisms underlying the ISM and its potential benefits.

Public attitudes toward FDI Screening Mechanism

Public attitudes toward sectoral coverage of FDI Screening Mechanism

The analysis above demonstrates that, unlike other countries in the region, Chile is at a considerably advanced stage in the ISM debate. The bill proposal correctly identifies mounting security challenges related to FDI and aims to establish an institutional framework to address potentially problematic transactions. However, the current process lacks a more specialized public and policy debate on the specific design elements that must be adopted for an effective ISM. The following section aims to advance such a debate by identifying these elements and proposing a potential ISM design for Chile.

Sectoral coverage

Among the first key considerations in designing a new ISM is defining the category of sensitive sectors, which will determine the scope of sectoral coverage. The most effective approach for Chile would be to develop a comprehensive economic security strategy. Such a strategy should first identify the main national interests in the economic realm and outline the principal tools to safeguard these interests, including ISM alongside other mechanisms such as supply chain resilience measures (See Serrano, 2026). The strategy should designate key economic activities and sectors critical to Chile's economic development and national secu-

20 rity. Currently, Chile lacks such a document. Existing policy documents, such as the National Cybersecurity Policy 2023-2028 or the National Lithium Strategy, focus only on specific industries. Similarly, existing security-related documents, such as the Book on Chilean National Defence 2017 or the National Defence Policy 2020, focus on traditional security domains and largely overlook economic security considerations.

As explained in the previous section, existing regulations in Chile reveal significant gaps in sectoral coverage. The number of sectors covered by any restrictions is very limited, leaving many key sectors currently unregulated. For instance, foreign ownership in electricity distribution—a sector in which Chinese SOE State Grid now dominates the Chilean market—is not currently regulated by Chilean law. As for the total number of sectors covered by an ISM, existing regimes broadly fall into two categories: those with a broad scope, covering a wide range of sectors or operating on a cross-sectoral basis, and those with a specific scope, targeting a more limited set of sectors deemed security-sensitive (Doppen et al., 2024). France exemplifies the broad approach, maintaining an extensive sectoral list that encompasses a wide array of strategic economic activities, while the Netherlands represents the specific approach, concentrating its screening mechanism on a more narrowly defined set of sectors (Ibid.). For Chile, the specific model appears more appropriate at this stage, given the country's economic profile and the relatively limited set of sectors in which incoming FDI raises genuine security concerns.

Regarding the concrete sectors to be covered by an ISM, Chile will mostly diverge from the experience of already established ISM regimes, predominantly those in North America and Europe. In those regions, policymakers frequently use ISMs to scrutinize or block FDI in dual-use sectors such as semiconductors or robotics, with other commonly covered sectors including

defense, cybersecurity, quantum technology, artificial intelligence, and biotechnology. However, given that Chile occupies a position as a consumer rather than a producer of technologies in these sectors, their inclusion in a Chilean ISM represents a secondary concern at present.

Based on the analysis of FDI flows above, sectors most critical to Chile's new ISM strategy should include energy infrastructure, such as production and distribution of gas and electricity. Given the significant share of Chinese FDI in infrastructure, railways, and hospitals should also be covered by the future ISM. Another essential sector is telecommunications, which is critical for national security and has witnessed growing presence of Chinese tech giants across the region in recent years. Given Chile's strategic location for space research and exploration, the ISM could also cover space-related activities. Finally, given Chile's location on the Pacific coast, FDI in major port infrastructure would also warrant inclusion in a future ISM, as has been the case in many other countries (Doppen et al., 2025). As the recent case of the Chinese-built port of Chancay illustrates, investment in this sector can similarly fuel debates about the erosion of national sovereignty (Briceño, 2026)

A specific category includes mining, especially copper and lithium. Chile currently has regulations that establish state control over mineral deposits but allow concessions to foreign companies. Considering the importance of these materials for great power competition, including them in the ISM would be warranted on both national security and economic competitiveness grounds. Regarding the latter consideration, greater control over which companies—whether foreign or domestic—gain access to extraction and/or processing of these materials could help the country specialize in higher value-added segments of the supply chain.

1.8%

1.16%

0.84%

0.7%

0.61%

0.33%

1.16%

5%

1

2

Type of FDI covered

Another key aspect of Chile's future ISM concerns the types of FDI transactions that will be subject to screening. Traditionally, M&A transactions have been central to debates and policies regulating FDI for national security purposes, primarily because host governments seek to protect leading domestic firms in key sectors from foreign takeovers (see Tingley et al., 2015). As explained above, M&A dominates recent Chinese FDI flows to Chile, suggesting this transaction type will likely remain the primary focus of Chilean ISM.

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Regarding greenfield investment, not all countries with ISMs include such transactions in their screening mechanisms, as they are generally perceived as less threatening to national security. Nevertheless, greenfield investments can pose security risks. For instance, the establishment of a new data center or other telecommunications infrastructure may create strategic dependencies on foreign providers who gain access to sensitive information about citizens and users in the host country. In Chile, companies such as Huawei have already undertaken greenfield FDI. In Chile, greenfield FDI from China represents less than 10% of total Chinese investment in the country since 2010. Moreover, the vast majority of these investments do not pose an immediate national security risk. Therefore, including this transaction type in the ISM remains of secondary importance at present.

Reviewing authority

In its path toward a formal ISM, Chile will also need to address another key decision concerning the type and composition of the review authority responsible for the screening process. Such an authority, situated within the executive branch, will play a leading role in the screening process. Existing practices point to two

main options. First, countries with ISMs may designate a specific ministry as the lead executive body responsible for FDI screening. In such cases, the designated ministry exercises significant control over the decision-making process, though it typically also solicits input from other ministries and state bodies. Countries following this model include France and Japan, where the Ministries of Economy and Finance, respectively, lead the screening process. The second main option entails creating a new institution exclusively dedicated to FDI screening. Such bodies typically possess dedicated expertise and budgets for tasks related to FDI screening. This approach corresponds to models such as the Committee on Foreign Investment in the United States (CFIUS) or Australia's Foreign Investment Review Board (FIRB).

Considering the existing institutional landscape in Chile, the government appears more likely to opt for the first option, with the role potentially granted to the Ministry of Finance. Conferring the role to an existing ministry would be prudent, as it would not entail excessive additional operating costs and would allow existing bureaucratic teams to leverage their expertise for these new tasks. However, it will be essential to ensure that the particular sectoral interests of the ministry are balanced by input from other relevant state bodies across different executive branches

Ideally, decisions by the Ministry of Finance, as the lead executive body of the ISM committee, should be preceded by consultations with other relevant state institutions. Drawing on the existing composition of Chile's Foreign Investment Committee would mean including the Minister of Economy, Development and Reconstruction; the Minister of Foreign Affairs; the Director of the National Planning Office; the Executive Vice President of the Production Development Corporation (CORFO); the President of the Central Bank of Chile; and the President of the Confederation of Production

and Commerce. Given the nature of the review—focused on preventing security threats from FDI—the committee would also benefit from input from all or some of the following bodies: the Ministry of Interior and Public Security; Ministry of National Defense; Ministry of Economy, Development and Tourism; Ministry of Mining; Ministry of Transport and Telecommunications; Ministry of National Assets; Ministry of Energy; Ministry of Science, Technology, Knowledge and Innovation; and Ministry of Public Works. Additionally, state intelligence bodies, such as the National Intelligence Agency (Agencia Nacional de Inteligencia, ANI), could be invited to participate in committee meetings and contribute their specialized expertise on specific sectors.

Other key considerations

The three elements discussed above represent the most essential components of Chile's future ISM design. In addition to these factors, Chilean authorities will also need to establish the minimum threshold, which corresponds to the minimum foreign stake in a transaction that will automatically trigger the FDI review process. Recent global trends indicate gradually decreasing thresholds. As such, for many reviewing countries, even a relatively small stake can lead to a screening process, as international standards typically set the threshold between 10 and 20% (Bauerle Danzman & Meunier, 2023).

As discussed above, the establishment of an ISM should not function as a tool discouraging foreign investors. To prevent this outcome, ISM design can incorporate voluntary consultation mechanisms. Under such provisions, foreign investors may submit voluntary requests

for non-binding consultations to determine whether a planned investment would be subject to FDI review. This tool helps foreign investors avoid unnecessary and undesirable financial and regulatory burdens, as well as reputational costs that can arise from blocked investments.¹²

Finally, Chile, along with other countries in the region, should remain aware of the current dynamics of intensifying US-China competition. Chile's position is particularly challenging in this regard, given its historically close political ties with Washington coupled with an increasingly dependent economic relationship with Beijing. Given Chile's strategic role in certain economic activities, such as critical minerals and space exploration, both great powers are likely to employ different tools to bring Chile into their respective orbits and align Santiago's policies with their geopolitical objectives. For ISM purposes, Chile should welcome advice and expertise from both countries, as well as from other powers, when shaping its future mechanism. However, policymakers should be careful not to antagonize relevant economic partners, which could result in undesired economic retaliation.

¹² Such a mechanism is currently in force in the Czech ISM, whereby foreign investors may proactively consult with the Ministry of Industry and Trade on a non-binding basis prior to proceeding with a given investment (Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic, n.d.).

IV. Conclusion

This report has examined Chile's path toward establishing a formal Investment Screening Mechanism by analyzing recent FDI trends, particularly from China, and assessing the country's existing regulatory framework. The analysis demonstrates that Chile faces a clear need to institutionalize an ISM, though this tool should be conceived as a preventive measure for specific transactions rather than a wholesale restriction on foreign investment. Crucially, such a mechanism should apply on a sector- and transaction-specific basis regardless of investor origin, avoiding the pitfall of targeting Chinese capital specifically and instead focusing on the nature and risk profile of individual deals. Between 2010 and 2024, China invested \$21 billion in Chile, with 91% concentrated in sensitive sectors such as energy, infrastructure, and mining. While most of these investments pose limited immediate security risks, exceptional cases—particularly State Grid's control over electricity distribution to 60% of Chilean households—illustrate the potential vulnerabilities that an ISM would address. The dominance of M&A transactions and the significant presence of Chinese SOEs further underscore the relevance of establishing formal screening procedures.

Chile's current legal architecture, while sophisticated in many respects, reveals significant gaps in addressing national security dimensions of FDI. The country lacks both comprehensive sectoral coverage and any state body with authority to review or block investments on national security or geopolitical grounds. Existing institutions, such as the Foreign Investment Committee and the National Economic Prosecutor's Office, serve facilitation and competition functions respectively, but neither is equipped to assess security externalities of FDI. This regulatory shortfall, combined with Chile's strategic importance in critical minerals and space exploration, creates vulnerabilities that could be exploited during periods of diplomatic tension or great power competition. In the absence of a formal screening mechanism, Chilean authorities have at times resorted to opaque and ad hoc measures to block or discourage sensitive transactions, a practice that undermines investor confidence and risks generating diplomatic

friction with the governments of affected investors. The 2020 bill proposal and subsequent parliamentary debate demonstrated growing awareness of these challenges among Chilean policymakers.

The successful implementation of an ISM in Chile will require addressing several critical design elements. First, Chile must develop a comprehensive economic security strategy that identifies national interests and designates which sectors warrant screening—likely including energy infrastructure, strategic ports, telecommunications, and mining. Second, Chilean authorities should designate the Ministry of Finance as the lead executive body, while incorporating input from the Ministries of Defence, Interior, and relevant sectoral ministries, as well as the National Intelligence Agency. This approach would leverage existing expertise without incurring excessive costs. Third, the mechanism should establish clear thresholds (typically 10-20% foreign stake) and incorporate voluntary consultation mechanisms to avoid discouraging legitimate investment.

Finally, Chile must navigate the geopolitical complexities of intensifying US-China competition while designing its ISM. Given Chile's historically close political ties with Washington and increasingly dependent economic relationship with Beijing, policymakers face the delicate challenge of strengthening regulatory capacity without antagonizing either major power. Chile should welcome technical advice and expertise from multiple countries when shaping its ISM, while ensuring that the mechanism serves Chilean national interests rather than external geopolitical agendas. A well-designed ISM could enhance rather than diminish Chile's attractiveness to foreign investors by providing greater legal certainty and demonstrating the country's commitment to balancing economic openness with strategic autonomy. The path forward requires sustained technical capacity-building, broader public awareness of ISM benefits, and political will to advance legislation that other Latin American countries will likely follow closely as they confront similar challenges in an era of renewed great power competition.

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